

COMPRESSIVE FAILURE UNDER FLEXURAL LOADING: EFFECTS OF SPECIMEN SIZE, STRAIN GRADIENT AND FIBRE WAVINESS

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SUMMARY: Recent experimental and finite element results are presented on factors affecting compressive failure of carbon fibre composites. Scaled flexural tests in a pin-ended buckling rig showed a 32% decrease in strain at failure for a factor of 8 increase in specimen dimensions. Tests on specimens with different lengths and widths but the same thickness suggested that the size effect was mainly due to the different strain gradients through the thickness. This was supported by constrained buckling tests where the ratio between compressive and flexural loading was varied. Fibre waviness was investigated with a surface profiling technique, and artificial waviness induced by laying up material on a curved panel which was straightened prior to curing. Finite element modelling of the effects of out-of-plane fibre waviness reproduced very well the trends observed experimentally.

KEYWORDS: compressive failure, flexural loading, strain gradient, size effects, shear instability, microbuckling, fibre waviness

INTRODUCTION

Compressive strength is an important factor in the design of composite structures, and consequently a great deal of research has been undertaken on failure under compressive loading. Despite this, there is still a lack of understanding of many aspects of compressive failure and the factors controlling it. This paper summarises experimental and analysis work carried out to try to develop a better understanding of some of these issues.

One question is the effect of specimen size. Reductions in strength with increasing stressed volume have been reported for a number of different failure modes [e.g. 1-4]. There have been suggestions of size effects in compressive failure [2,5], although the difficulties of obtaining reliable test results make this harder to establish. Results are presented here of a series of scaled buckling tests on unidirectional carbon fibre-epoxy which show an unequivocal reduction in compressive strain at failure with increasing specimen size [6].

This size effect could be due to differences in stressed volume, or it could be due to differences in the stress or strain gradient through the thickness, which a number of modelling studies have shown to have a significant effect on compressive strength [7-9]. This has been investigated with a new constrained buckling rig which enables the ratio of compressive to

flexural loading to be varied independently of the specimen size [10]. Results presented show a definite effect of strain gradient on compressive strain at failure.

Fibre waviness has received much more attention, and a number of studies of natural and artificially induced waviness have been published [e.g. 11-14]. Results are reported here of measurements of fibre waviness in the same material as that used for the other experiments [15]. Artificial waviness has also been generated, and its effects on compressive failure under flexural loading studied [15].

Compressive failure in many composites is believed to be caused by shear instability, sometimes referred to as microbuckling. Finite element analysis of this failure mechanism has been undertaken, and comparisons made with the experimental results.

EFFECT OF SPECIMEN SIZE

Tests were performed on unidirectional T800/924 carbon fibre-epoxy specimens in the pin-ended buckling rig shown in Fig. 1 [6]. This produces flexural failure in the gauge length, avoiding any stress concentration effects. Three sets of tests were carried out with all specimen and test rig dimensions geometrically scaled. Specimens were 1, 2 and 8 mm thick, machined out of the same 66-ply panel of material. Strain gauges at the centre of the specimens on each surface were used to measure the strain at failure.

Fig. 1: Medium sized pin-ended buckling rig and specimen (dimensions in mm)

Specimen size (mm)	Failure strain (cv), %		Number of specimens
	compressive	tensile	
200 x 40 x 8	-1.47 (1.9)	1.13 (6.1)	4
50 x 10 x 2	-1.77 (5.6)	1.35 (3.2)	9
25 x 5 x 1	-2.16 (5.7)	1.67 (2.7)	7
150 x 40 x 2	-1.82 (8.2)	1.54 (7.7)	15
150 x 10 x 2	-1.89 (5.2)	1.57 (5.6)	15
30 x 10 x 2	-1.89 (9.6)	1.06 (11.3)	15

Table 1: Results of pin-ended buckling tests

All specimens behaved similarly, with catastrophic failure, and consistent compressive failures in the gauge length. The results are presented in the top half of Table 1. There is a 32% decrease in strain at failure with the factor of 8 increase in all specimen dimensions.

Three further sets of tests were conducted where the thickness was kept constant and the length and width of the specimens varied. These specimens were cut from a 2 mm thick plate of the same material. Strains at failure were all very similar, as shown in the lower half of Table 1. This suggests that the size effect observed with the scaled specimens is most likely to be due to the reduction in strain gradient with increasing specimen thickness rather than a statistical effect due to differences in stressed volume.

The results for all six sets of tests are plotted in Fig. 2 as a function of the strain gradient, defined as the difference in surface strains at the centre of the specimen at failure divided by

Fig. 2: Strain gradient effect with different sized specimens

the thickness. A least squares straight line has been put through the scaled results, and gives a good fit. The results for the second set of tests are slightly above the line, which could be because the specimens were cut from a thinner plate where the fibre alignment may have been better.

EFFECT OF STRAIN GRADIENT

A new buckling rig was developed which allowed the ends of the specimen to rotate initially, and then lock up [10]. By changing the amount of rotation permitted, the ratio between compression and bending could be varied.

Fig. 3 shows the rig. The specimen (12) is clamped to end fittings (10) which can rotate on pins (3). Adjustable tie rods (5) lock the rig after a certain amount of rotation, effectively changing the end conditions from pinned to clamped.

Two different sized specimens were tested, both 2 mm thick and 10 mm wide, with gauge lengths of 20 mm and 40 mm. Initial tests were carried out to determine the range of rotation angles which gave consistent gauge length failures. Two sets of tests were then undertaken for each length with the minimum and maximum rotation angles.

All specimens failed in the gauge length, with similar compressive failures to those obtained in the pinned ended buckling tests. The strains at failure were measured with strain gauges at the centre of the specimens. For the 20 mm gauge length case with the minimum rotation angle there was some asymmetry in the response which meant that the maximum strain did not necessarily occur at the centre of the specimen. In this case the maximum strains were estimated from the readings of three strain gauge at different positions along the length.

Fig. 3: Constrained buckling rig

Specimen size (mm)	Rotation Angle (deg)	Failure strain (cv), % compressive	Failure strain (cv), % tensile	Number of specimens
40 x 10 x 2	20	-1.94 (7.5)	1.53 (6.0)	5
40 x 10 x 2	5	-1.77 (4.8)	1.11 (8.7)	6
20 x 10 x 2	13	-1.80 (3.7)	1.24 (7.2)	5
20 x 10 x 2	1	-1.61 (5.2)	0.25 (60.9)	6

Table 2: Results of constrained buckling tests

Fig. 4 shows the results for all four sets of tests plotted against the strain gradient through the thickness, and the values are given in Table 2. There is a consistent trend, with a 20% increase in strain at failure for a 85% increase in strain gradient through the thickness. The results cannot be explained in terms of statistical effects due to differences in stressed volume. The trend is similar to that obtained with the pin-ended buckling tests, and provides further support for the conclusion that the strain gradient through the thickness is critical in determining the compressive strain at failure.

EFFECT OF FIBRE WAVINESS

A technique was developed for measuring out-of-plane waviness using a surface displacement transducer mounted on a traversing table [15]. Measurements within the laminate were made by splitting it open along ply interfaces treated with release agent prior to curing.

Fig. 5 shows typical results in terms of the out-of-plane misalignment angles at the centre of a 2 mm thick T800/924 plate, measured along a 120 mm length in the fibre direction. The

Fig. 4: Strain gradient effect with different ratios of compression to bending

Fig. 5: Out-of-plane misalignment angles, runs at 1 mm pitch across width offset by 1 degree

successive traces are at 1 mm increments across the width, offset by 1 degree for clarity. Most of the angles lie within a range of ± 0.5 degrees, with maximum misalignments of about 1 degree. There is little correlation between the different traces, showing that the waviness is localised to relatively small areas. These angles are relatively small, and it is possible that the technique underestimates the true misalignments of the fibres. It has been assumed that the surface profile of the split open panels represents the geometry of the fibres, but resin on the surface could tend to smooth out undulations in the plies.

Similar measurements at other ply interfaces showed that the misalignment angles were highest near the centre of the panel, reducing in magnitude towards the surfaces.

Artificial waviness was produced by laying up unidirectional prepreg on a curved plate, and then straightening it before curing [15]. This gave severe in-plane waviness in the centre of the upper surface, but no signs of waviness on the lower surface. Two panels were made, one of which included release agent in the lay-up to enable it to be split open to measure the waviness.

Out-of-plane misalignment angles were similar to those from the flat panel with no artificially induced waviness, with peak values of about 1 degree near the centre of the panel. After splitting the panel through the thickness along the release treated interfaces, the resulting two ply thick layers were split along their length. The splits followed the fibres, allowing the in-plane waviness to be measured by examining the geometry of the splits under the microscope. Severe misalignment angles of up to 24 deg. were found at the surface, reducing to up to about 6 deg. in plies 3 and 4. No significant in-plane waviness was observed deeper than ply 4.

Specimens 50 x 10 mm were cut from the non release treated panel with their centres in the middle of the worst kinks. They were tested to failure in the pin-ended buckling rig with the side of the specimen with waviness on the compression surface. The behaviour was very similar to that of the previously tested ones with nominally straight material. The mean compressive strain at failure was 1.46%, a reduction of 17%. The scatter was also considerably increased, with a coefficient of variation of 16.4%.

The relatively small reduction in strain at failure is rather surprising considering the severity of the waviness. However, the waviness was largely in-plane, and limited to the surface. Modelling studies have shown that where waviness changes over short distances, the strength is determined more by the average misalignment angle, and so small areas of poor alignment would not be expected to have such a great effect [16]. This is also consistent with previous results where localised areas of naturally occurring waviness on the surface were found to have negligible effect on compressive strains at failure [6].

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

An approach developed previously [8,14,16] was used to analyse the effect of the strain gradient on compressive failure due to shear instability. A 2-D finite element model was prepared of a section of material subject to pure bending. The representation of fibre waviness was greatly simplified. All waviness was assumed to be out-of-plane, with a sinusoidal waveform and constant amplitude through the thickness. Beam elements were used to model the fibre direction properties, and continuum elements to represent the transverse and shear properties of the composite. This hybrid approach allows the fibre bending stiffness to be included, and models correctly the change in material axes which occurs under shear deformation.

A short section of 0.25 mm was modelled, corresponding to one half wavelength. The amplitude was such as to give a maximum misalignment angle of 2 degrees. These values were chosen arbitrarily as the basis of a parametric study before any measurements had been made. In fact, the observed wavelengths were greater than this and the maximum misalignments measured were somewhat less. Boundary conditions and loading were applied to model a continuous beam with constant waviness subject to bending with no axial load. The model is shown in Fig. 6. Further details can be found elsewhere of the modelling approach [16] and its application to flexural loading [8].

Measured non-linear fibre direction and shear properties for T800/924 were used [14]. The transverse response was assumed to be linear. Three different models were analysed, 1, 2 and 8 mm thick, corresponding to the three thicknesses of beams investigated in the pin-

Fig. 6: Typical finite element mesh and boundary conditions (waviness exaggerated)

ended buckling tests. In all cases a maximum moment was obtained at which the response became unstable. The surface strains at this point were taken as the failure strains.

Results are presented in Fig. 7 in terms of the compressive strains at failure as a function of the strain gradient through the thickness. There is a strong trend of increasing strain at failure with decreasing thickness, as shown previously [8]. The misalignment caused by the waviness produces shear stresses in the highly loaded surface region. This in turn produces increased misalignment, and at a certain point the process becomes unstable leading to catastrophic collapse. As the strain gradient increases, the less highly loaded fibres away from the surface are able to provide more support, increasing the stress at which instability occurs.

The 2 mm thick model was rerun with a combination of direct compressive and bending loading instead of pure bending. The surface compressive strains at onset of instability as a function of strain gradient fitted very closely with the results for pure bending on the different thickness specimens. This shows that the strain gradient is the critical parameter, irrespective of whether it varies due to changes in thickness or changes in the ratio of compressive to flexural loading. The same conclusion was drawn from the two series of tests presented earlier.

The experimental results from the scaled pin-ended buckling and constrained buckling tests are also shown on Fig. 7. The trends shown in the analysis and test results are very similar. The actual strains at failure are higher than predicted for a number of reasons. Firstly the analysis was based on arbitrarily assumed waviness parameters. The measured maximum misalignment angles were up to about 1 degree compared with the 2 degrees assumed in the model. The wavelength used was also shorter than typical measured values. The amplitude was assumed to be constant, whereas in fact it tends to decrease towards the surface of the

Fig. 7: Predicted strain gradient effect and comparison with test results

panel. All three factors would tend to increase the strain at failure [8,16], and if they were all accounted for in the model, the predicted strains would be greater than the measured ones.

On the other hand the model also makes a number of simplifying assumptions that would tend to overestimate the strain to failure. It is a 2-D model, and neglects the effect of in-plane waviness, which may combine with that out of the plane to produce higher effective waviness. The model assumes that the shear response is independent of the fibre direction strain, neglecting any interaction which may occur in practice. It also neglects the effects of overall shear stresses which are present in the pin-ended buckling tests due to the end load and the angle that develops during the test as a result of the bending. Any tendency for creep to occur due to the high shear stresses in the areas of waviness is ignored.

Clearly compressive failure is a very complex problem. Excellent qualitative agreement has been obtained between the model and the experimental trends, and the analysis has provided a better understanding of the effects of the different parameters. However, quantitative comparisons are made difficult by the assumptions required in the analysis, and uncertainties with regard to the appropriate parameters to represent fibre waviness realistically.

CONCLUSIONS

The strain gradient through the thickness is a critical parameter affecting the compressive strain at failure under flexural loading. This has been demonstrated by scaled tests in a pin-ended buckling rig, by constrained buckling tests varying the ratio between compressive and flexural loading, and by finite element modelling accounting for the effect of out-of-plane fibre waviness. Size effects observed in the scaled tests are predominantly due to the changes in the strain gradient with different thicknesses, rather than due to the different stressed volumes.

Out-of-plane ply level misalignment angles of up to about 1 degree have been measured. Highest values were near the centre, decreasing towards the surface, and with significant variations across the width.

Specimens with severe fibre waviness induced on the surface showed only a 17% reduction in compressive strain at failure when tested in the pin-ended buckling rig. This is thought to be because the waviness was mainly in-plane, and limited to the region close to the surface.

Finite element modelling of the shear instability failure mechanism was able to reproduce very well the trends observed experimentally, and can give valuable insight into the factors affecting failure.

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